

Upper and Lower Bounds of Near Square Prime Counting Function

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Abstract

The counting function, $\Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{N})$, or the number of near square primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$ that are less than or equal to a larger natural number, \mathbf{N} , likely satisfies the following conditions:

$$\mathbf{k}_1 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 < \Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) < \mathbf{k}_3 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}), \text{ or}$$

$$\mathbf{k}_2 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}) < \Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) < \mathbf{k}_3 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}),$$

where \mathbf{k}_1 , \mathbf{k}_2 , & \mathbf{k}_3 , are constants. \mathbf{k}_2 and \mathbf{k}_3 could be approximately 1.5 and 1.6, respectively based on limited data.

The conditions are also applicable for other near square primes of the forms such as $\mathbf{n}^2 + 2$, $\mathbf{n}^2 - 2$, $\mathbf{n}^2 \pm \mathbf{n} \pm 1$, etc., but with different values of \mathbf{k}_1 , \mathbf{k}_2 , & \mathbf{k}_3 , respectively.

I. Introduction

The near square prime counting function, $\Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{N})$, which is the number of primes that are of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$, where \mathbf{n} is a natural number, and are less than or equal to a larger natural number, \mathbf{N} , has been disclosed,^[1] as shown in the following:

$$\Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) \sim \mathbf{N}^{1/2} \times (1 - r_{p_1/p_1})(1 - r_{p_2/p_2})(1 - r_{p_3/p_3})(1 - r_{p_4/p_4}) \dots (1 - r_{p_y/p_y}) - 1 + \Pi_{ns}(p_y), \quad (1)$$

and

$$\Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) > 2\mathbf{C}(p_y) \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2, \quad (2)$$

where $2 = p_1 < p_2 < p_3 < p_4 < \dots < p_y$ are consecutive prime numbers, $p_y^2 \sim \mathbf{N}$, r_{p_x} , $x = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$, y , are the numbers of removed residue classes (0 mod p_x), and $\mathbf{C}(p_y) = (1 - 1/2^2)(1 - 1/4^2)(1 - 1/6^2) \dots [1 - 1/(p_y - 1)^2]$ is the twin prime constant according to the first Hardy-Littlewood conjecture. Eq. (2) establishes a lower bound for the near square prime counting function.

In this paper, larger lower bounds are disclosed, and some possible upper and lower bounds are conjectured.

II. Lower and Upper Bounds of Near Square Prime Counting Function

Based on indication of the Chinese remainder theorem, the near square prime counting function, $\Pi_{ns}(N)$, in Eq. (1) is generated by precluding the $n^2 + 1$ values in the residue class (0 mod p_x) for all $p_x^2 \leq N$ from a set of natural numbers, $S_n = \{n^2 + 1 | n \text{ is a natural number, and } 1 \leq n^2 + 1 \leq N\}$, where N is a large natural number. Since $r_{p1} = 1$, and every r_{px} , $x = 2, 3, 4, \dots$, y , in Eq. (1) is either 0 or 2,^[1] it is obvious that there are many lower bounds that are larger than that of Eq. (2). For example, $r_{p2} = 0$, and, compared to Eq. (2), Eq. (1) for $N \geq r_{p2}^2$ can result in

$$\Pi_{ns}(N) > 3 \times 2C(p_y) \times N^{1/2}/[\ln(N)]^2 = 3C(p_y) \times N^{1/2}/[\ln(N)] \quad (3)$$

Let $f_{cns}(p_x) = (p_x - r_{px}) / (p_x - 2)$ for $x > 1$, and $f_{cns}(p_1) = (p_1 - r_{p1}) / (p_1 - 1) = 2 - r_{p1}$. Then for $x > 1$, $f_{cns}(p_x) = p_x / (p_x - 2)$ when $r_{px} = 0$, $f_{cns}(p_x) = (p_x - 1) / (p_x - 2)$ when $r_{px} = 1$, and $f_{cns}(p_x) = 1$ when $r_{px} = 2$. Thus, Eq. (1) becomes

$$\Pi_{ns}(N) \sim N^{1/2} \times F_{cns}(p_y) (1 - 1/p_1)(1 - 2/p_2)(1 - 2/p_3)(1 - 2/p_4) \dots (1 - 2/p_y) - 1 + \Pi_{ns}(p_y), \quad (4)$$

where $F_{cns}(p_y) = f_{cns}(p_1)f_{cns}(p_2)f_{cns}(p_3)f_{cns}(p_4) \dots f_{cns}(p_y)$, and Eq. (2) becomes

$$\Pi_{ns}(N) > F_{cns}(p_y) \times 2C(p_y) \times N^{1/2}/[\ln(N)]^2 \quad (5)$$

It's been found that $r_{p2} = r_{p4} = r_{p5} = r_{p8} = r_{p9} = 0$. Thus,

$$F_{cns}(p_2) = 3/(3-2) = 3$$

$$F_{cns}(p_4) = 3 \times 7/(7-2) = 21/5 = 4.2$$

$$F_{cns}(p_5) = (21/5) \times 11/(11-2) = 77/15 \sim 5.1333$$

$$F_{cns}(p_8) = (77/15) \times 19/(19-2) = 1463/255 \sim 5.7373 \sim \ln(p_8^2)$$

$$F_{cns}(p_9) = (1463/255) \times 23/(23-2) = 4807/765 \sim 6.2837 \sim \ln(p_9^2)$$

If $F_{cns}(p_y)$ is finite and equal to some constant k_1 when $p_y^2 \sim N$ goes to infinity, Eq. (5) results in

$$\Pi_{ns}(N) > k_1 \times N^{1/2}/[\ln(N)]^2 \quad (6)$$

There is a possibility that $F_{cns}(p_y)$ is infinite when $p_y^2 \sim N$ goes to infinity, and $F_{cns}(p_y)$ might be proportional to $\ln(N)$. Thus, Eq. (5) might become

$$\Pi_{ns}(N) > k_2 \times N^{1/2}/\ln(N), \quad (7)$$

where k_2 is a constant.

The ratio of the number of near square primes in S_n to the total $N^{1/2}$ values is likely to be less than or approximately equal to $[\ln(N)]^{-1}$, similar to the prime number ratio. Thus, there might also exist a constant k_3 such that

$$\boldsymbol{\pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) < \mathbf{k}_3 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}) \quad (8)$$

Combining Eqs. (6) & (8), and Eqs. (7) & (8), respectively, results in

$$\mathbf{k}_1 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/[\ln(\mathbf{N})]^2 < \boldsymbol{\pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) < \mathbf{k}_3 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}) \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{k}_2 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}) < \boldsymbol{\pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) < \mathbf{k}_3 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}) \quad (10)$$

In fact, some limited data appear that, approximately,

$$1.5 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}) < \boldsymbol{\pi}_{ns}(\mathbf{N}) < 1.6 \times \mathbf{N}^{1/2}/\ln(\mathbf{N}). \quad (11)$$

III. Conclusion and Discussion

While there are infinitely many near square primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$,^[1] there possibly exists upper and lower bounds, as shown in Eqs. (9) & (10). Further works are necessary to verify.

The results discussed in this paper and the prior one^[1] are valid for near square primes of other 2nd order polynomial forms with integer coefficients, $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n})$, such as $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{n}^2 + 2$, $\mathbf{n}^2 - 2$, $\mathbf{n}^2 \pm \mathbf{n} \pm 1$, etc., because there are at most 2 different incongruent residues, \mathbf{r}_1 & \mathbf{r}_2 , such that $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}_1) = \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}_2) = 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$ for every prime \mathbf{p} . Using $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{n}^2 + \mathbf{n} + 1$ as an example, if

$$\mathbf{r}_2 \equiv \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{r}_1 - 1 \equiv -(\mathbf{r}_1 + 1) \pmod{\mathbf{p}}, \text{ then}$$

$$\mathbf{r}_2 + \mathbf{r}_1 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$$

$$\Rightarrow (\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1)(\mathbf{r}_2 + \mathbf{r}_1 + 1) \equiv \mathbf{r}_2^2 + \mathbf{r}_2 + 1 - (\mathbf{r}_1^2 + \mathbf{r}_1 + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathbf{r}_1^2 + \mathbf{r}_1 + 1 \equiv \mathbf{r}_2^2 + \mathbf{r}_2 + 1 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}.$$

Thus, there are 0, 1, or 2 residue classes of \mathbf{p} such that $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathbf{p}}$ for all \mathbf{n} values in the residue classes, and Eqs. 4-10 are valid. In this case, $\mathbf{r}_{p1}=0$, $\mathbf{r}_{p2}=1$, $\mathbf{r}_{p3}=0$, $\mathbf{r}_{p4}=2$, $\mathbf{r}_{p5}=0$, resulting in $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_1)=2$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_2)=2$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_3)=5/3$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_4)=1$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5)=11/9$, respectively, and $\mathbf{F}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5) = \mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_1)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_2)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_3)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_4)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5) \sim 8.1481$. Compared to $\mathbf{F}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5) \sim 5.133$ for $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{n}^2 + 1$, there are more primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + \mathbf{n} + 1$ than those of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + 1$.

This is similar to prime \mathbf{k} -tuple counting functions^[2] and Goldbach's comet of the Goldbach function, on which smaller primes have more impacts.^[3,4] When there are more small prime values with $\mathbf{r}_p=0$ for a particular $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n})$, there are more primes of the form $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n})$. For example, when $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{n}^2 + \mathbf{n} - 1$, $\mathbf{r}_{p1}=0$, $\mathbf{r}_{p2}=0$, $\mathbf{r}_{p3}=1$, $\mathbf{r}_{p4}=0$, $\mathbf{r}_{p5}=2$, resulting in $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_1)=2$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_2)=3$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_3)=4/3$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_4)=7/5$, $\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5)=1$, respectively, and $\mathbf{F}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5) = \mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_1)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_2)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_3)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_4)\mathbf{f}_{cns}(\mathbf{p}_5) = 11.2$. There are even more primes of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + \mathbf{n} - 1$ than those of the form $\mathbf{n}^2 + \mathbf{n} + 1$.

It has to be cautious that the discussions above are valid only when $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n})$ is not divisible by any first order polynomial. Those are not valid if $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n})$ equals to multiplication of 2 first order polynomial, e.g. $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{n}^2 - 1 = (\mathbf{n} + 1)(\mathbf{n} - 1)$. In this case, precluding the residue classes, $(1 \bmod \mathbf{p})$ and $(-1 \bmod \mathbf{p})$ for each \mathbf{p} up to \mathbf{p}_y is equivalent to finding the twin prime pairs of the form $(\mathbf{n}-1, \mathbf{n}+1)$ in between \mathbf{p}_y and \mathbf{p}_y^2 . Each remaining \mathbf{n} value corresponds to a $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n})$ value equals to the multiplication of the 2 twin prime elements, and is obviously not a prime. Thus, $\Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{p}_y^2) - \Pi_{ns}(\mathbf{p}_y) = 0$ for $\mathbf{p}_y > 2$, and Eq. (1) and others are not valid.

The sieve method with the indication of the Chinese remainder theorem can be implemented to find the number of divisible polynomial values that are the multiplication of prime factors. For example, the values of the form $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{n}) = (6\mathbf{n}+1)(12\mathbf{n}+1)(18\mathbf{n}+1)$ is a Chernick's Carmichael number when all 3 factors are prime numbers.^[5] The counting of prime 3-tuple of the form $(6\mathbf{n}+1, 12\mathbf{n}+1, 18\mathbf{n}+1)$ that are less than or equal to a large natural number, $\mathbf{N} \sim (6\mathbf{m}+1)(12\mathbf{m}+1)(18\mathbf{m}+1)$, is approximately^[2]

$$6 \times 2.857 \times \mathbf{m} / [\ln(18\mathbf{m})]^3 + 6 \times 2.857 \times \mathbf{m}^{1/2} / [\ln(18\mathbf{m}^{1/2})]^3$$

$$\sim 17.142(\mathbf{N}/6/12/18)^{1/3} / [\ln(18(\mathbf{N}/6/12/18)^{1/3})]^3 + 17.142(\mathbf{N}/6/12/18)^{1/6} / [\ln(18(\mathbf{N}/6/12/18)^{1/6})]^3$$

For $\mathbf{N} = 10^{15}$, it is ~ 94 , which is much smaller than the 150212 Carmichael numbers reported by Pinch.^[6] Nevertheless, it does show that there are infinite counts of Chernick's Carmichael number which is a subset of all Carmichael numbers. Thus, there exists infinite Carmichael numbers.

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V. Reference

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